

Time-Resolved In-Line UV/VIS/NIR Spectroscopy: A Customized Setup for the Investigation of the Flow-Synthesis of Plasmonic Patchy Particles

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Abstract:

Kinetic measurements can play an important supporting role in the development of plasmonic nanoparticle synthesis. Specifically, they provide crucial insights into the reaction dynamics, and nucleation and growth phenomena that ultimately influence particle morphology and properties. Here we present an innovative in-line monitoring system developed to investigate the flow synthesis of silver patches on silica core particles. Our custom-built setup comprises a 3D-printed T-mixer directly connected to a glass tube. Using a computer controlled linear stage, the position of a fiber-coupled UV-VIS-NIR spectrometer along the glass tube can be arbitrarily set in order to obtain an extinction spectrum at early reaction times. Moreover, a second glass tube, connected to the first with an arbitrary long spacer tube enables later reaction times to be probed. We give details of the determination of characteristic mixing time of the T-mixer-tube combination and show how raw spectral data from growing silver patches can be processed and analysed. This leads to the acquisition of valuable data concerning the patch formation kinetics. Our work offers fresh insights into the potential of in-line spectroscopic monitoring systems for application to similar nanoparticle systems with strong dependency of the optical properties on morphology.

Keywords: Spectrometric analysis; Reaction kinetics; Nanoparticle synthesis; Villermaux-Dushman Protocol; Reaction Monitoring

Article Highlights:

- Custom-built system for in-line spectroscopic monitoring of flow synthesis at arbitrary reaction time.
- Comprehensive data processing methodology for extracting kinetic information.
- Application of the system to study the formation of plasmonic patchy particles.

Plasmonic nanoparticles, especially those comprised of nanostructured noble metals, have seen burgeoning interest in recent decades. These materials exhibit unique light-matter interactions, which render their optical

properties tunable across a broad spectrum, ranging from the visible to the infrared electromagnetic regions [1]. This attribute underpins the potential of plasmonic nanoparticles in a wealth of applications, including sensing,[2] spectroscopy [3], photothermal therapy [4], (photo/electro)catalysis [5, 6], solar energy conversion [7], and pigments [8]. However, these exciting prospects are significantly curtailed by the limited availability of synthetic methodologies that are tunable, scalable and reproducible. In our previous work, we addressed this shortcoming by developing a novel electroless synthesis for the formation of silver patches on non-functionalized silica spheres [9, 10]. Our initial batch process was later adapted to a continuous flow millimixer environment [11], leading to a scalable and highly reproducible synthetic route. Further refinements, including the pre-seeding of patches, enabled greater control over silver growth, thereby broadening the tunability of the localized surface plasmon resonances to a range of at least 900 nm [12]. Despite the simplicity of our approach, it can access a wide variety of rather complex patch morphologies [10]. To fully exploit this in applications it is essential to obtain a detailed understanding of the process-structure relationship. Here, *in situ* spectroscopic investigations, which make use of the fact that growing metal nanostructures provide an optical signature of their morphology, can play a key role [13, 14]. Continuous flow reactors are ideal for *in situ* i.e, in-line, process diagnostics, but most studies on nanoparticle synthesis have used the stopped flow technique or taken measurements at fixed locations [13]. To fully understand process dynamics, time-resolved measurements at various reaction times are necessary, especially for the formation of complex plasmonic nanostructures like metal patches, where morphological changes significantly affect the plasmon resonances.

In the present study, we introduce an innovative in-line spectroscopic setup, designed for real-time, high-resolution monitoring of silver patch growth from a few hundred milliseconds after mixing up to more than 10 seconds. This custom-built device captures UV-VIS-NIR extinction spectra at arbitrary times following the mixing of reactants in a T-mixer, yielding unprecedented insights into the silver patch growth process. Here, we will detail the design, properties, and operation of this in-line spectroscopic setup and thereby lay the groundwork for a future article analysing acquired kinetic data for a wide range of synthetic conditions.

When designing the in-line spectroscopic setup, we considered several key criteria. Firstly, the device should be compatible with our synthetic system, namely the electroless deposition of silver patches through the reduction of silver nitrate by formaldehyde in dilute ammonia solution in the presence of gold nanocrystal-seeded core silica particles [12]. Secondly, spectroscopic measurements should be able to resolve key features in the extinction spectrum of the silver-silica patchy particles, specifically the patch thickness-dependent out-of-plane quadrupole resonance at 330-340 nm [15], and the patch thickness and coverage dependent in-plane dipole resonance between

400 nm and 1300 nm [12]. Thirdly, measurements should be conducted during continuous flow synthesis without perturbing or halting the stream. Fourthly, the system should be able to collect data from a wide range of times after the reactants meet at a T-mixer, from as early as possible to over 10 seconds (the approximate duration of the reaction). Finally, for ease of comparison, the setup should be on a similar scale as our preparative continuous flow setup [12], the chosen design compatible with the higher flow rates necessary for gram-scale production runs Fig. 1a and 1b shows a 3D model and photograph of the setup, respectively. The apparatus comprises two 30 cm long borosilicate glass tubes with rectangular inner dimensions of 7x3 mm (C M Scientific Ltd, UK). During initial tests using as-received glass tubes we noticed that deposits of silver were formed on the inner walls of the entrance of the tube closest to where the reaction mixture enters (Fig. 1c). This was not particularly surprising since our synthetic process relies on the coulombic attraction of positively charged silver ions to negatively core silica particles. We therefore functionalized the glass with N-[3-(Trimethoxysilyl)propyl]-N,N,N-trimethylammonium chloride (TMAC) to give the surface a positive charge and thereby repel silver ions. Firstly the tubes were activated by treatment with a ten times diluted base piranha solution (5 parts H₂O, 1 part NH₄OH, 1 part 30% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) – N.B. Extreme caution must be used when preparing and handling base piranha solution). Next they were immersed for 40 hours in an ethanolic solution of 2% TMAC and 10 mM HCl. Finally the tubes were flushed with KNO₃ to exchange any residual Cl⁻ ions and then with ultrapure water. Following this treatment no further significant deposition of silver on the glass was observed.

As shown in Figs. 1a and 1b, the glass flow tubes are mounted within a frame. The inlet of the lower glass tube ("Front" tube) is inserted into a specially designed 3D printed T-mixer (see insets in Figs. 1a and 1b). The interior of the latter matches the dimensions of the glass tube, a rectangular EPDM rubber ring being employed to ensure a tight compression seal. A similar approach is used for the exit of the first glass tube, as well as both ends of the upper glass tube ("Back" tube), which are connected to straight 3D-printed connectors (see insets in Figs. 1a and 1b). Silicone tubes are connected to the inlets of the T-mixer, and polyamide tubing, as used in our other continuous flow setups [12], serves as a spacer junction between the front and back glass tubes. This junction consists of two 3-way stopcocks with Luer connections. Depending on the range of reaction times required in the back tube, these stopcocks can either provide a shortcut from the front to back tubes or a connection to a spacer tube of arbitrary length. The internal diameter of the polyamide spacer tubing was chosen to be 5/16" in order to

closely match the Reynolds number in the glass tubes. The reagents are delivered to the T-mixer by means of a two-channel syringe pump (Legato 270, KD Scientific Inc, USA) using 200 mL syringes.

Fig. 1. a) 3D-models of the continuous flow in-line spectroscopic setup in addition to the rectangular T-mixer and connectors. b) Photograph of the setup. A two-channel syringe pump, not shown in the photo, delivers Reservoir 1 and 2 to the 3D-printed T-mixer (see left inset) connected to the lower glass tube ("front" tube). The reaction progresses along the front tube and leaves it via a 3D-printed connector (see right inset). The flow then passes a spacer tube junction – here the shortcut is shown – and enters the upper glass tube ("back" tube). Fibers from the lamp and to the spectrometer are connected to a fixed post in either the upper or lower position depending on the reaction times to be measured. To set the reaction time, the frame holding the glass tubes is driven by a linear stage to the correct position. c) Photograph of the part of an untreated glass tube where the T-mixer was situated following several reaction runs.

The frame holding the front and back glass tubes is affixed to a linear translation stage (LTM120 from OWIS GmbH, Germany), itself immobilized on an optical breadboard (See Figs. 1a and 1b). This arrangement enables

the computer-controlled translation of the glass reaction tubes through a fixed measurement post. Borings in the latter accommodate collimating lenses which connect to fibers coming from and leading to a light source (Avalight-DH-S-Bal, from Avantes BV, Netherlands) and double-channel spectrometer (Avaspec UV-VIS-NIR, also Avantes), respectively. In the optical path between the source and receiver fibers, the glass reaction tubes are oriented to expose their longer side to the lenses. The choice of rectangular tubes was deliberate to avoid light distortion on curved glass surfaces and to simplify optical alignment. Moreover, their size was carefully chosen to permit a sufficiently high flow rate at the same time as providing a long path length, thus ensuring high extinction. To avoid potential fluctuations in the light beam due to movement of the optical fibers, the measurement position is fixed and the glass tubes themselves are translated by the linear stage. The effective translation range relative to the measurement position is 24 cm, with 3 cm on either end accounted for by the fixation posts and the lengths that the tubes are inserted into the T-mixer and connectors.

While the pump was operated manually, a computer program was developed to simultaneously control the linear stage and obtain raw data from the spectrometer (LabVIEW, National Instruments Corp. USA). This application determines the current position of the stage and calculates the corresponding reaction time based on the given tube size and flow rate.

As with any newly established continuous flow millimixing process, prior to investigating the target reaction, it is important to ascertain the flowrate dependent characteristic mixing time. This is especially pertinent in the present case as we need to be aware of which measurement points in the front tube correspond to a situation of incomplete mixing. To determine the characteristic mixing time we used the well-known Villermaux-Dushman reaction in the protocol detailed by Commenge and Falk [16]. The chemical system comprises an alkaline-buffered (NaOH and H₃BO₃) solution of potassium iodide (KI) and potassium iodate (KIO₃), mixed with an acid, typically H₂SO₄, in the mixer under scrutiny. Spectroscopic analysis is then used to deduce the mixing time from the absorbance of the resulting solution, a variable which hinges on the triiodide (I³⁻) concentration. Two simultaneous chemical reactions underpin the system: the nearly instantaneous neutralization of the acid and a much slower formation of iodine, which consumes six moles of protons. The reactions are as follows:

In a perfectly mixed system, the reaction (II) does not occur as all protons are consumed during neutralization (I). However, imperfections in mixing and the emergence of local concentration gradients result in iodine formation via (II). The slower or less efficient the mixing, the more iodine can form, which further combines with excess iodide to form triiodide via (III). The characteristic absorption of triiodide at 353 nm is then measured using UV-VIS spectroscopy.

Commenge and Falk established a master curve, which correlates the measured extinction with the mixing time, and they proposed an equation to calculate the characteristic mixing time (t_m) [16]:

$$t_m = 0.33(\text{OD}) [H^+]^{-4.55} [KI]^{-1.5} [KIO_3]^{5.8} [NaOH]^{-2} [H_3BO_3]^{-2} \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), OD denotes the optical density (extinction) normalized to the pathlength used (10 mm in the present work). The formation of triiodide naturally depends on the concentration of the components. Commenge and Falk recommend several concentration sets that can be employed for mixers with mixing times spanning from a few milliseconds to several seconds. In our experiments, we used concentration set 2c [16]. The mixing time of our 3D-printed T-mixer coupled to the front glass tube was characterized at flow rates varying from 25 to 300 ml/min per syringe in 25 ml/min steps, as well as the maximum flow rate of 317 ml/min per syringe. These flow rates correspond to a Reynolds number range from 167 to 2113. For each flow rate, three experiments were performed, the samples collected and measured using a benchtop UV/VIS spectrometer (Lambda 35, Perkin Elmer). From Equation (1) a range of characteristic mixing times between 160 ms at the highest flow rate and 1200 ms at lowest flow rate were determined. Fig. 2a shows the logarithm of the mixing time versus the logarithm of the Reynolds number. With the exception of the lowest Reynolds number, the data lie on a straight line, similar to what Commenge and Falk report and consistent with our earlier work [11, 16]. As the lowest flow rate experiment was seen to lead to a stratified flow (see inset of Fig. 2a) or sometimes even showed incomplete filling of the tube, the corresponding datapoint understandably does not fit the global trend.

Knowing the dimensions of the glass tube, we could determine the position corresponding to the characteristic mixing times for each flow rate used (see Fig. 2b). Interestingly, for flow rates apart from the lowest, this position remains rather constant, approximately 9 cm away from the T-mixer. The nine measurement positions in chain mode (see below) are also shown in Fig. 2b. It can be seen that the first two measurements are scheduled prior to complete mixing and the third slightly after it. This is important information which must be considered in our detailed studies of metal patch growth kinetics to be reported in a future publication.

Fig. 2. a) Characteristic mixing time versus Reynolds number for the 3D-printed T-mixer/front glass tube combination. Inset: photograph of the front tube during the lowest flow rate experiment showing the layering of the flow. b) Position in the glass tube corresponding to the determined mixing times versus the flowrate. The measurement positions of the chain mode of operation of the in-line spectroscopic setup (see main text) are also indicated.

Having ascertained the relationship between flow rate and characteristic mixing time and identified how far into the front tube the flow can be considered fully mixed, we will now demonstrate the reaction time resolved measurement of spectra for growing silver patches on silica spheres. For this, one inlet of the T-mixer is fed with an aqueous solution of gold-nanocrystal seeded 483 nm diameter silica core particles, silver nitrate and formaldehyde, while dilute ammonia solution is provided to the other inlet. Further details of the reaction procedure can be found in a recent article [12].

The system was designed with two general modes of operation in mind. Firstly, a single measurement mode, where the position of the motor can be manually adjusted. Secondly, a so-called “chain mode” where the glass tubes are automatically driven to nine different positions along the entire available range. The chain mode aims to efficiently use the limited operation time of the continuous flow process to acquire data for a range of reaction times. At each position the linear stage pauses for a duration of at least 250 ms. This allows for the spectrometer integration time (typically 2.5 ms) and the number of spectra acquired and averaged (typically 100). Considering both the travel time between measurement positions and the need for short buffers before the start and after the end of spectra acquisition, the complete chain measurement requires about 70 seconds. Due to the limited syringe size and to allow for starting up of the continuous flow reactor we selected a flow rate of 100 mL/min per syringe. This corresponds to a characteristic mixing time of 567 ms and, as indicated in Fig. 2a, lies well within the “normal” behaviour of the mixer.

During the chain mode operation, a dark, reference, and sample spectrum are collected at each measurement point. The extinction is computed from the raw counts (I_i) given by the detectors for each pixel using the formula:

$$E = \log\left(\frac{I_{ref} - I_{dark}}{I_{sample} - I_{dark}}\right) \quad (2)$$

In the usual workflow, the dark measurement is conducted first, with the spectrometer shutter closed and the pump off. Then, the sample measurement is taken while the reactants are being pumped through the system. After this, the system is flushed with ultrapure water and the reference measurement is taken while the water is pumped through. This measurement order is used to account for any residual silver deposition on the glass walls during the reaction, despite the TMAC functionalization mentioned above.

Fig. 3 shows spectra from the two spectrometer channels for a typical patchy particle sample. Relevant plasmonic features are the out-of-plane quadrupole resonance at ~330 nm and the in-plane dipole resonance at ~850 nm. The UV-VIS channel of the spectrometer contains 2048 pixels and is capable of measuring wavelengths within a range of approximately 176 to 1336 nm and average resolution of 0.56 nm. However, due to low detector sensitivity, data collected below approximately 280 nm and above 1000 nm are prone to significant noise. The NIR detector gathers data between 853 and 1867 nm across 256 pixels with an average resolution of 4.13 nm. As wavelengths beyond 1350 nm are increasingly absorbed by water, data collected by the NIR detector in this region also suffers from considerable noise. The raw data is processed as follows: After the extinction has been calculated, the data from the UV-VIS and NIR channels are smoothed using a 11-point (i.e. ± 2.80 nm) and 3-point (i.e. ± 4.13 nm) moving average, respectively. A larger averaging window for the UV-VIS detector would result in the loss of the UV-peak, which should be avoided due to the high value of this peak in determining patch thickness [15]. Next, the data is interpolated to a consistent resolution of 1 nm. During this interpolation step, data from both channels are concatenated at 900 nm. In some samples, a slight vertical offset between the extinctions of the UV-VIS and NIR detectors is observed. This discrepancy is corrected by shifting the NIR spectrum by the difference between the points at 900 nm (UV-VIS) and 901 nm (NIR), as depicted in Fig. 3. The noisy regions of the data are discarded during interpolation, and only the final spectrum (blue line in Fig. 3) between 300 and 1300 nm is considered for further analysis.

Fig. 3. Raw extinction data collected from the UV-VIS (grey) and NIR (red) spectrometer channels. Both spectra are concatenated at 900 nm with the NIR portion being corrected by the offset, resulting in the final spectrum (blue).

As the chain mode scans the entirety of the available range of a glass tube in a single run, this results in a block of nine measurements. To cover the total time it takes for the reaction to complete, chain measurements are performed once in the front tube, i.e. directly after the mixer, and multiple times in the back tube using the shortcut or spacer tubes of varying lengths. This leads to multiple blocks of measurements for each sample. The reagents are freshly prepared for each of these blocks. In case of fluctuations between measurements, reagents were prepared multiple times. While most measurements used a total of 150 ml of reagent solution in each syringe, for longer spacer tubes, this was increased to 200 ml.

Fig. 4a shows exemplary measured spectra from a single set of reaction conditions. The latter were arranged so that the dimensionless ratio of silver atoms in the precursor to gold nanocrystals attached to the silica core particles as defined in our recent work was 1.22×10^6 [12]. The blocks of data correspond to the front tube (group 1) and the back tube, using the shortcut (group 2) and spacer tubes of 47 cm (group 3), 93 cm (group 4), and 139 cm

(group 5), respectively. These lengths were chosen to provide an equally spaced temporal separation between the measurement blocks and were used for most experiments. Overall, a reaction time range between 225 ms and 13.6 seconds was probed here. However, the spectrum is seen to develop in about two thirds of the total time and remains approximately unchanged for the remainder. This corresponds to a time to reaction completion of around 10 seconds, similar to that determined for batch *in situ* measurements [10]. In the early stages of the reaction, the signal from the developing in-plane dipole resonance peak around 800 nm is barely visible against the silica nanospheres scattering background. Moreover, the UV-peak is barely visible even in the final phases. To address these issues, the scattering baseline of the core particles is removed, leaving only the spectrum due to the silver patches (Fig. 4b). By removing the background scattering, the new peak positions are slightly red-shifted and are more easily identified and analysed. Since the spectrum still contains some noise, the two peaks are fitted with Gaussian functions to determine these points of interest. The peaks are often skewed, so a simple Gaussian fit is not sufficient. Therefore, they are fitted using 3-term Gaussian functions. The peak height is then determined from the maximum of the corresponding 3-term function within the fitting range, while the peak wavelength corresponds to the wavelength at that maximum. This process mitigates the minor fluctuations of the height and positions caused by noise.

Fig. 4c and 4d show the extracted peak height and peak wavelength versus reaction time data for the sample. Both datasets contain important information which, when compared with samples produced at many other reaction conditions as is planned for an upcoming publication, can assist with identifying the growth mechanism and kinetics and provide the foundation for a predictive model for patch formation.

In conclusion, we have successfully developed an innovative in-line system for the monitoring of the formation of silver patches on silica core particles. The integrated use of UV-VIS and NIR detectors, accompanied by systematic data acquisition and analysis, demonstrated significant potential in providing useful data. As such, our approach forms a strong foundation for future studies seeking to understand and optimize silver patch synthesis and is likely applicable to study the continuous flow synthesis of other types of plasmonic nanoparticles. This includes a related synthetic system based on the deposition of plasmon resonant gold patches on cationic polystyrene cores [17]. The insights gained from our research reinforce the value of in-line monitoring as an essential tool for applications where precision, efficiency, and consistency in nanoparticle synthesis are of paramount importance.

Fig. 4. a) Example of extinction spectra data (following smoothing and interpolation) gathered for silver patches growing on gold-nanocrystal seeded silica core particles using five separate chain measurements. b) the spectra in a following baseline correction. c) Plot of dipole plasmon resonance peak wavelength versus reaction time extracted from the spectra in b). d) Plot of dipole peak extinction versus reaction time extracted from the spectra in b).

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Statements and Declarations

Conflict of interest: The authors state that there is no conflict of interest.

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